

STRATEGIC OPPORTUNITIES AND CHALLENGES OF THE MIDDLE CORRIDOR IN GEORGIA**David Tchiotashvili***Doctor of Economics, Professor of Gori State University,
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ORCID-0000-0001-6795-9484***Abstract**

The Middle Corridor is an important transit route between China and Europe, and its strategic importance is obvious for the countries along the corridor, as it is not only a transit bridge, but also a mechanism for economic diversification and stability in the face of geopolitical changes. The aim of the paper is to analyze the strategic opportunities, current situation, challenges and prospects of the Middle Corridor, to identify it as an attractive alternative to the Russian and Mediterranean routes, and to determine the economic and geopolitical significance of the existing project. It is also important to determine how the Middle Corridor can be made a competitive, fast and sustainable international transport route, mainly in the direction of Georgia, Azerbaijan, Kazakhstan and Turkey.

Keywords: Middle Corridor; Cargo Traffic Regulation; Foreign Trade; Strategic Economic Policy; Financial Policy.

Introduction: For Georgia, the Middle Corridor represents a crucial opportunity to develop a strategic transport corridor on its territory, connecting Chinese regions with European markets, via Azerbaijan, Georgia and Turkey. The first steps in the development of the Middle Corridor were unpredictable and uneven. Challenges included different standards, inadequate development of port networks and inefficient customs procedures. However, in 2013, a large-scale regional joint initiative based on international support began the consistent development of the Middle Corridor. In 2014, the Trans-Kazakhstan Railway was completed, and in 2017, the Baku-Tbilisi-Kars Railway was fully operational, significantly improving the potential and efficiency of the Middle Corridor. After Russia's invasion of Ukraine, the Middle Corridor took on significant economic, financial and political significance. Due to international sanctions, the operation of the Northern Corridor through Russia has been significantly restricted. As a result, the demand for diversification of cargo flows between China and Europe has increased, which has led to the importance of the Middle Corridor based on economic trends.

Statistics show that the Middle Corridor is actually already developing rapidly: cargo turnover increased in 2021–2024, and by 2030, the projected volume of transit cargo is expected to increase even more. In terms of duration, the duration of cargo delivery through the corridor is significantly reduced, which is a significant improvement compared to other routes, but, despite the fact that the relevant infrastructure has been developing, especially in recent years, the main challenges remain the limited cargo throughput capacity of seaports and railway lines, imperfect capacity, ineffective relevant customs procedures, and some economic and political instability in the countries of the Middle Corridor project. The results of the current study show that the Middle Corridor has actually been developing rapidly in recent times: cargo turnover has increased from 1.5

million tons to almost 2.8 million tons (+86%), and the projected volume for 2024 has increased to 4–4.2 million tons.

Review: Freight transportation via the Middle Corridor is an important factor in the geopolitical and economic transformation of the Eurasian system as an alternative to the Northern Route, although its further development and diversification became necessary after Russia's invasion of Ukraine, which dramatically changed the global logistics picture and made the Caucasus an alternative route for countries seeking to reduce their dependence on Russian transit. In response to this challenge, in November 2022, Azerbaijan, Georgia, Kazakhstan, and Turkey signed a “roadmap” that identifies priority investment areas, including the modernization of ports, railways, and customs procedures. In June 2023, the same countries created a single logistics operator to ensure the effective functioning of the Middle Corridor, monitoring cargo movements, and immediate resolution of problems. International organizations, the World Bank, and the European Union have confirmed their readiness to support the project with investments and technical assistance. These projects include both infrastructure and the implementation of digital solutions, from cargo tracking systems to customs digital platforms.

For the Central Asian countries, the emergence of direct access to the EU through the Middle Corridor has brought significant geopolitical benefits, which was reflected in a 33% increase in container flows on this route in 2022. However, this sharp increase in demand soon turned into serious infrastructure challenges, which was compounded by a lack of investment. As a result, shipments in the first eight months of 2023 decreased by 37% compared to the previous year. This shows that the real potential of the Middle Corridor cannot be fully exploited without improving processes and modernizing logistics systems. According to the trade model, China-EU trade will grow by about 30%

by 2030, especially in the import-oriented direction. Exports of raw materials and energy resources from Kazakhstan are expected to increase by 10-15%, while exports of agricultural products from Georgia and Azerbaijan are also forecast to grow significantly.

The main strategy and economic benefits of the Middle Corridor are reflected in the following key factors: improving infrastructure (modernization of railways, construction of new roads and highways, and port terminals); increasing access to international markets (increasing investment, inflow of foreign capital, and technological innovations); diversifying the economy (reducing dependence on traditional trade routes and strengthening regional integration); developing the business sector, tourism sector, and logistics (manufacturing, small and medium-sized businesses, e-commerce, tourism services, hotels, new tourist routes, increased visitor flow, fast delivery, logistics, and transport services).

Significant challenges include the constant change of transport modes along the corridor; the inconsistency of standard, legislative and bureaucratic mechanisms between participating countries; and unregulated coordination between operators. The Middle Corridor brings together hundreds of specialized logistics companies and government agencies, without a single, effective central management body that could coordinate, transfer data in real time, and synchronize processes. Trade modeling has shown that by 2030, the capacity of goods transported through the corridor will triple to about 11 million tons. This model is based on an overall 30% increase in China-EU trade, an average of +5% per year in GDP, and an increase in throughput by 10–25% through cost and time optimization. Transportation times could be reduced to 12–14 days, depending on infrastructure development and coordination in the region.

Conclusion: The Middle Corridor has the strategic potential to become one of the main transcontinental transport routes connecting Europe and Asia. Its full-fledged development goes beyond its logistical function and acquires a much broader economic and social significance. The effective functioning of the corridor not only ensures the integration and diversification of regional economies, but also opens up new opportunities for both states and the private sector. Modernization of infrastructure, development of the railway network, improvement of ports and road junctions will become the basis for development, which will significantly reduce transportation costs and time losses. As a result, access to markets will increase and the export potential of the participating countries will be strengthened. An improved logistics environment will make the region particularly attractive for foreign

investment, which will increase the likelihood of development of local manufacturing and high-tech sectors. In addition, the development of the corridor contributes to the activation of tourism, improving infrastructure access and the emergence of new transport routes, which will make the region more accessible and attractive for international visitors. This will create valuable additional income for the local economy, especially in micro-regions that were previously left behind in logistics networks. In addition to economic benefits, the development of the Middle Corridor has an important geopolitical dimension, reducing dependence on traditional trade routes and creating new alternatives strengthens the independence of the participating countries and increases their foreign trade positions.

Despite the significant potential, the full implementation of the Middle Corridor requires systematic work on existing challenges. Infrastructure imperfections, the complexity of customs procedures, administrative obstacles to transit and the lack of coordination between countries require solutions. Overcoming these problems will be possible only through coordinated international cooperation, consolidated efforts of the public and private sectors. It is necessary to improve the investment environment, strategic planning of transport policy and the introduction of technological innovations, which will make the process predictable and sustainable.

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